

Advanced Manufacturing Technologies
Medicine and Biology

Mobility and Transportation Systems
Production Technology

Information and Communication Technologies
Lightning and Display

Create Your Business in Photonics!

France - Germany - Italy
Netherlands - Slovakia
Sweden - UK

Security and Defense
Photonics for the Life Sciences

Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light

Why create your business in Photonics? Why introduce photonics technologies in your existing business?

There are many potential benefits of using photonics technologies in your company, as they are relevant in regards with societal challenges and less-costly to use.

This guide provides you with information about technologies and related sectors needing photonics technologies to develop themselves in France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Slovakia, Sweden, and UK.

A focus on specific regions is available, with data on mature photonics technologies and photonics applications relevant for the future including market description, technologies, trends, challenges, and opportunities.

A special section on support for entrepreneurship in Photonics in these regions is also available.

Table of content

France	p.6
Germany	p.10
Italy	p.14
Netherlands	p.18
Slovakia	p.22
Sweden	p.26
UK	p.30

FRANCE

Photonics was selected within the Paris region “Ile de France” strategy as a vector for industrial development. France is one of the three pioneers in the field of Photonics (besides USA and Germany).

The Paris region represents more than 40% of the industry and research in Photonics in France. The industrial ecosystem is very rich and includes world leaders like Thales and innovative SMEs, like Amplitude Technologies (ultra-fast lasers). The region is the European leader in terms of scientific publications and/or patents in several application fields involving Photonics technologies.

In terms of business opportunities, some gaps exist in the value chain in the field of industrial processes, mainly in terms of systems integrators. Technology transfer is strongly encouraged by the French government.

Mature photonics technologies

Lasers are one of the technologies presenting a high potential to a very important number of applicative domains. According to their characteristics (amplitude, wavelength, pulse duration...), lasers can be used in academic research, industrial processing, medical diagnosis and treatment. The Paris region possess both pioneer results on academic topics like ultrashort high intensity pulse lasers and world leading technologies in the industrial or medical fields. Among the current R&D topics, we can find the development of intense femtosecond lasers working at high rates.

The field of Photonics also provides a vast number of advanced sensors that offer numerous ways to measure, evaluate and control devices, their properties and performance. Different types of photonics sensors exist based on different principles and technologies: lasers, imaging systems, fiber... The Paris region gathers a strong SMEs ecosystem specialized on different sensor technologies: infrared and visible imagery, optical fiber, pollutants detection... The main current challenge is related to managing and exploiting the vast amount of heterogeneous information obtained from sensors, independently of the application domain (medical imaging, industrial process control, ...).

PHOTONICS APPLICATIONS RELEVANT FOR THE FUTURE

Advanced Manufacturing Technologies

Technologies and trends: an increasing number of material processing are based on lasers (soldering, cutting, 3D printing ...) and integrate Photonic sensors for quality and process control on the production and assembly lines.

Challenges: taking into account industrial constraints, in terms of productivity (3D printing) or data processing associated to automatic control and inspection.

Opportunities: SMEs, start-ups and high government funding form the innovation engine for the fourth industrial revolution in Germany.

Mobility and Transportation Systems

Technologies and trends: one of the current trends in the field of terrestrial transportation systems is the autonomous and intelligent vehicles. It's highly dependent on the "Photonics" technologies: sensors, cameras and LIDAR for observing the environment, LEDs and lasers for smart lighting and vehicle to car and infrastructure communications, displays for HCI, augmented/virtual reality, optical fibers for in-vehicle communications... "Fly by Light" is another trend in aeronautics: the optical fibers for in-vehicle communication infrastructure present several advantages in terms of weight and resistance to interference.

Medicine and Biology

Market description: market with a large volume and strong growth. The photonics have a significant and strategic place on the medical and biological technologies (biological measurement, monitoring, ophthalmic glass...).

Technologies: spectroscopy, medical imaging, advanced microscopy, lasers...

Trends, challenges and Opportunities: one of the current trends is the self-measurement. The key needs are non-invasive sensors with immediate result, easily integrated in electronics devices. Photonics technologies answer these key needs.

Smart and sustainable city

Market description: market with a medium volume composed by some niche markets and a good growth. Photonics have an important place in the building management but especially in the communication infrastructures, energy and light production.

Technologies, trends, challenges, opportunities: a significant trend is the development of the air quality management where Photonics provide solutions. The Li-Fi is an important response to the needs of interaction people or machine vs infrastructures. Photovoltaic is of course also a key technology.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

Market description: The most dynamic market is data transmission driven by IOT which requires high band with wireless communications, and more optical fiber.

Technologies: Access Network: FTTH: DWDM, E-PON, G-PON, NG-PON / Home network: WIFI; LIFI.

Opportunities: miniaturization of devices by using silicon photonics, decrease power consumption of components to decrease generated heat, high speed at long distances with low optical losses, enhance WIFI usage, introduction of LiFi in home network...

Security and Defense

Market description: mid-size market, with high added value, where Photonics plays a key and historic role. The French market includes leading European and worldwide players relying on a strong research. The market is important but not well-founded enough, prompting companies to export. Market strongly linked to government requirements and constraints.

Technologies, trends, challenges and opportunities: high strategic impact for the States. Foot soldier's equipment and stealth detection equipment are underlying trends. Optronics and lasers are central.

Support for entrepreneurship in Photonics in the Paris region

- “Défi Photonique” program : financial support up to 50% of consulting fees to help photonics companies in their strategic and business development
- Testimony: « The market study highlighted a strong demand on manufacturing; it is thus relevant for us to reinforce this aspect.” – Frédéric BERIER, EvoSens.
- Innovative and business development department in Opticsvalley (regional photonics cluster): diagnosis and support for the development of your innovative strategy, matchmaking, visibility...
- Contact & information: Fiona GERENTE – f.gerente@opticsvalley.org

GERMANY

Photonics is one of the most important industries of the future and key technologies in Germany and it is an essential part of the High Tech Strategy of the Federal Government.

With world market leaders such as Leica, Osram, Trumpf, Sick, Schott, Carl Zeiss, Coherent Laser Systems, Karl Storz, Leybold Optics and Nanoscribe and numerous SMEs, start-ups and research institutions in Germany all disciplines of photonics are represented. Reinforced cooperation between business and science, as well as high investment in research and development are reflected in the increased dynamics of innovation in German photonics.

Mature photonics technologies

The production technology as one of the core areas of the German photonics industry with significant global market share is concerned with laser materials processing and production control in industrial manufacturing.

In macrotechnology laser are used for separating and joining processes such as cutting, welding, drilling, soldering, cleaning, structuring or polishing, for example in the automotive industry. In microtechnology, for example in the lithographically manufacture of integrated, ultra-short pulsed lasers are used.

In the fields of mechanical engineering, automotive, manufacturing and process automation as well as biotechnology and environmental technology, optical sensors are used, e.g. for presence, position and quality control. Laser scanners, photocells, rangefinders and systems for material analysis are just a few examples of various methods to test, control and optimize manufacturing processes.

PHOTONICS APPLICATIONS RELEVANT FOR THE FUTURE

Production Technology

Technologies and trends: Laser material processing (welding, cutting, drilling, ...) as well as the optical sensors gain increasingly in importance in industrial manufacturing and quality assurance.

Challenges: There is an increased demand for more accurate material-processing systems and intelligent optical sensor system in the context of the Industry 4.0.

Opportunities: SMEs, start-ups and high government funding form the innovation engine for the fourth industrial revolution in Germany..

Image processing and metrology

Technologies and trends: The demand for testing systems for surface inspection, optical 3D measurement and X-ray and the material analysis is constantly increasing.

Challenges: Trends shaping e.g. in the field of mobility, the high-tech factory and consumer electronics.

Opportunities: Increase Open Innovation processes for higher cooperation of large manufacturers, innovative SMEs, start-ups and research institutions.

Medical & Life Science

Technologies: Modern microscopes, imaging in medicine, laser therapy and endoscopy systems and those for biotechnology and pharmaceutical research gain increasingly in importance in our society.

Opportunities: (Young) scientists can develop new markets and enjoy all the benefits of multidisciplinary research and development in this interdisciplinary area.

Communication Technology

Technologies: Optical transmission systems, whether open-air or fiber bonded have great potential in terms of transfer rate and encryption technology.

Challenges: The Internet of Things and communication technology for the end user as well as the security and defense technology pose present and future major challenges.

Information Technology

Technologies and trends: For example, digital image sensors for cameras or scanners for barcodes are innovative growth markets for the industry. Information technology is indispensable for the optical communication. One day, the optical could replace the electronic data processing.

Challenges: Optical data memory and processors are a forward-looking approach to compliance of Moore's Law.

Optical components and systems

Technologies: Systems for laser material processing and lithography as well as for image processing and illumination optics require optical components. Users are the electrical and electronics industry, including the semiconductor and display industries, and the automotive industry.

Opportunities: Optical design and simulation is becoming increasingly complex and gains in importance in other sectors such as architectural importance.

Unterstützung des Unternehmertums im Bereich Photonik in Deutschland

- Das Förderprogramm, Photonik Forschung Deutschland“ des Bundesministeriums für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) beinhaltet Ausschreibungen zu verschiedenen Themenfeldern.
- OptecNet Deutschland, als Zusammenschluss der regionalen Innovationsnetze für Optische Technologien fördert die Vernetzung von Wirtschaft, Wissenschaft und Politik, initiiert internationale Kooperationen, unterstützt Innovationsprozesse und fördert Start-ups
- Kontakt & information: +49 511 277-1643 | optecnet@optecnet.de | www.optecnet.de

ITALY

Photonics in Trentino Alto Adige

Although the Trentino Alto Adige region is an alpine country, mainly devoted to tourism and agriculture, the Provincia Autonoma di Trento and Bolzano allocate a percentage of their PIL, higher than the national one, to researcher and development. The Provincia Autonoma is supporting the establishment of new technological startups mainly in the field of ICT, digital economy, green economy and smart cities. For this reason, the local government has established a system of incentives for companies interested in investing in Trentino and has launched a set of government agencies supporting the business and the internationalization.

Mature photonics technologies

Many companies are present on the Trentino Alto Adige territory with the aim to develop new, low cost and high performances devices exploiting different technologies and useful in the different fields in order to move towards a region economically and socially sustainable. Typical examples are: in-line control of products and monitoring of manufacturing processes; innovative low noise and high performance silicon photomultipliers, design and manufacturing of high-performance digital cameras for industrial, scientific, medical, traffic, and security applications and for the recognition of wood defects, grades and classifies lumber with high precision.

A complementary technology field concerns the use of lasers that allow the development of machine tools for tube manufacturing and micromachining that can find application in different fields such as automotive, furniture, agricultural machinery, aerospace and structural steel.

PHOTONICS APPLICATIONS RELEVANT FOR THE FUTURE

Information and Communication Technologies

Market description: the market has huge volume and strong growth where photonics has a strategic role.

Technologies, trends, challenges: core optical network, backhauling e fronthauling, radio-over-fiber, Indoor optical communications, software-defined optical networks, optical interconnections, Mode Division Multiplexing, quantum communications.

Opportunities: Technologies for Pb/s optical networks, optical technologies for ubiquitous mobile and fixed access, high-speed access technologies.

Industrial Manufacturing and Quality

Market description: global market with good perspectives with good perspectives of development of manufacturing and employment.

Challenges: development of laser sources (mainly active-fiber lasers) for cutting (beam shaping, new laser wavelengths), welding (flexibility, system architecture, smart and adaptive systems), additive industries, micro manufacturing (surface functionalization).

Opportunities: Italy has to keep the leading position in the production of laser systems and innovative applications.

Life Sciences and Health

Market description: biophotonics is the third global industry of photonics sector (38% increase rate over the past 10 years). Strong social impact as it responds to the growing expectations of a better quality of life. Biophotonics has a strong economic impact, being it able to contain the costs for health care spending with the early diagnosis and minimally invasive therapies.

Challenges: Instruments based on laser, LED, lamps for light therapy and minimally invasive surgery. Devices for self-diagnosis and point-of-care. Diagnostic devices and imaging/microscopy to new early diagnosis.

Lightning and Display

Market description: expanding market for new lightning technologies, where Italian industry, worldwide renowned, must continue to play an important role.

Technologies, trends, challenges: increase the reliability of materials and equipment of LED lighting, develop (O)LED intelligent lighting systems, increase energy efficiency and lighting comfort, identify the quality criteria for the products on the market, encouraging the consumer adoption of new light sources. Integration of the new generation of light sources in the architecture for the «smart cities» and «ambient assisted living».

Security, Metrology and Sensors

Market description: security is an expanding market due to political instability and terrorism. Many companies are active in Italy in the area of security.

Technologies, trends, challenges: Laser sensors for monitoring environmental parameters, sensors for food control and safety, point sensors for toxic or illegal substances, sensors for border monitoring via optical fiber networks, fiber optic sensors for geophysical/biomedical/monitoring applications.

Opportunities: the very strong acceleration of the world market will foster the economic growth and employment.

Design and Manufacturing of Components and Systems

Market description: optical communications require components for optical and electro-optical devices capable of managing several hundred Gbit/s per wavelength, with low fuel consumption (to below the pJ/bit).

Technologies, trends, challenges: development of technologies for innovative optical materials for photonics (glass, semiconductors, polymers), for integration of photonic circuits different materials, for micro-positioning and automatic fixing, for integration with electronics, for the automation of production processes and test methods, for optical fibers.

Support for entrepreneurship in Photonics in Italy

- European Project LightJumps <http://www.lightjumps.eu/>
- European Project OASIS <http://www.fp7-oasis.eu/> limited to bio-agroindustrial and life-science sectors
- Business incubators: support structures for startups spread all over Italy
- Grandi Progetti PAT: <http://www.uniricerca.provincia.tn.it/>

NETHERLANDS

Photonics is part of the High Tech Systems & Materials (HTSM) topsector policy of the Dutch Government.

The Photonics R&D agenda has been assigned by the HTSM top team to roadmaps which are an integral part of the Innovation contract of HTSM with the government.

The Netherlands has a strong scientific position in important photonics segments and a highly qualified high tech industry that can bring photonics into numerous markets. Dutch internationals like ASML, Philips and OCE/Canon are big players in the photonics area and the Netherlands has also more than 200 SMEs which are already embracing photonics for innovation. A smart photonics ecosystem has been realized covering different important value chains. Finally also the regional government of the south-east of the Netherlands embraced photonics with an own so called Photon Delta Program that is focused on the further industrialization of Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs).

Mature photonics technologies

Lasers, lenses, light sources, mirrors and opto-electronic devices are important subsystems of the production machines of wafers for the semiconductor industry in the Netherlands. ASML, the Dutch supplier of production equipment for wafers to produce integrated circuits covers about 80% of the world market. A challenge for ASML is the introduction of a new extreme ultra violet (EUV) light source to be able to produce circuits with smaller nanostructures.

The Dutch Photonics sector also has strong international positions in medical instruments (imaging, detection, diagnostics) and printing (copiers) industries. The main current challenge is to organize the industrialization of all possible value chains for applications that use photonics based technologies.

PHOTONICS APPLICATIONS RELEVANT FOR THE FUTURE

Advanced Manufacturing technologies

Important challenge: The semiconductor focused ecosystem in the south of the Netherlands wants to come to the industrialization of Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs). In PICs functionality is based on the processing of optical signals in different building blocks. It is expected that PICs will follow a similar route that the electronic integrated circuits industry did 20-30 years ago. Important parts of the supply chain already are very active. The challenge is to come to more PICs based applications.

Medical Instruments

Market description: market with a strong growth. All medical systems comprise a combination of photonic components (lasers, detectors, lenses), microelectronics, mechanics and software.

Technologies: Spectroscopy, imaging, advanced microscopy, different other diagnostic systems, therapeutic laser systems.

Trends, challenges: Miniaturization of the systems is often desirable to bring the instruments towards the practitioner/patient..

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

Market description: The ICT market with its applications of TVs, computers and phones continuous to be an important dynamic market and will be driven by IOT, wireless broadband, datacom with new antenna systems based on optical interconnects, and so on.

Technologies: WIFI, LIFI, FTTH, GPON, WDM-PON, ...

Challenge: The main challenges in product development are on-chip integration and miniaturization by using integrated photonics (PICs).

Horticulture and agrofood

Market description: Growth stimulating lighting systems, photonics based sensors for monitoring of climate and growth conditions in greenhouses, photonic trace gas detection for monitoring of crop conditions in the field and in stores, monitoring of soil conditions (fertilization) and salt-fresh water ratios, quality monitoring of packed nutrition and fruit, and so on.

Challenge: The effective and efficient organization of the value chains.

Big science

Market description: Big science programs are becoming more important and have great economic impact. Examples of big science projects where photonics based instruments plays significant roles are CERN, ITER, ESRF, ESS, E-ELT, HFML, ESA and ESO.

Dutch companies are quite active in these networks.

Challenges: Improvement of the interaction between government, researchers and supplying industry; Pushing of technology boundaries.

Various

Market description: Further there are many other market segments where Dutch companies play important roles to develop photonics based applications. Examples of markets are defense & security, earth & environmental observation, industry, and so on.

Examples of product market combinations are OLED, spectroscopy, copiers, solar panel production equipment, sensors, cameras, and so on.

Support for entrepreneurship in Photonics in The Netherlands

- **Programs with financial support:** In the Netherlands there has been a small decade of financial support for the R&D of photonic devices. This program stops December 2015. More generic national programs for further R&D will stay in the future. Also Horizon 2020 will be used. Finally the regional Photon Delta program with a focus on integrated photonics will start in 2016.
- **Networking support:** Support comes from the national cluster PhotonicsNL. Further each year there is the national Photonics Event with a meet & match. Company missions are organized to different parts of the world. Also a network is discussing about the start of the Dutch Optical Centre (DOC) in 2016. The DOC is planned to be product oriented.
- **Contact & Information:** René de Groot - E-mail: rene.de.groot@kvk.nl

SLOVAKIA

Photonics is mostly unrecognized and underdeveloped as individual entity in Slovakia, however strong perspectives do exist in the fields where Photonics is used as technological solution.

The industrial ecosystem related to Photonics in Slovakia is fragmented, although strong companies and partners do exist e.g. in Display, Automotive, Lightning or Creative industry areas. Connections between industry and academic institutions are limited, but improvement in this field is one of the key issues being addressed by the current policy of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic. Technology transfer is strongly encouraged by the Slovak government, however related activities of Slovak academic groups in photonics are still marginal and global companies in most instances do not directly collaborate with the local academic institutions in R@D activities.

Mature photonics technologies

Display technology is one of the key photonics technologies that has a high perspective in Slovakia. The undisputed leaders of this field are currently Foxconn Slovakia and Samsung, represented by Samsung Display Slovakia (SDSK) and Samsung Electronics Slovakia. The other past major investor in this field – Taiwan based global company AU Optronics unfortunately announced end of production of its display unit in Slovakia in 2013, keeping just service capacities. Closely related to the display manufacturing, Panasonic Industrial Devices Slovakia is a global producer of electronic components. Last but not least, Slovak company Kvant had become one of the leading European developers and manufacturers of high quality laser display systems and laser show solutions, linking photonics to the Creative Industry which had been identified as one of the key enabling technologies for the future in Slovak business environment.

Another field tightly connected to Photonics is Automotive industry, which is currently one of the largest industrial sectors in Slovakia. Major global manufacturers such as Volkswagen group, PSA Peugeot Citroën and KIA Motors Slovakia have their manufacturing plants in western and central Slovakia, making this region one of the largest producers of cars per capita in the world. Related to automotive and mechanical engineering, Laser technology is a traditional area of photonics applications in Slovakia. The strongest industrial market members are currently First welding company, Industrial institute of Slovak Republic, Microstep and many other, smaller companies.

Lightning and energy is a field where advances provided by photonics technologies plays a central role. In this area, companies such as Siemens and Philips are the most active players, sharing their interest also in medical imaging technologies. There are also large number of local companies such as LIGHT Spectrum, Helios Lightning, TopLight, Smart Light, LEDeco solution, OMS, etc. involved in distribution and development of various lightning solutions and products.

Fiber optics and telecommunication is the last strong industrial sector where photonic solutions finds its use in practice. In addition to traditional global telecommunication companies, local market is based on manufacturers of fiberoptic components and solutions such as Sylex or Optocon.

PHOTONICS APPLICATIONS RELEVANT FOR THE FUTURE

Advanced Manufacturing technologies

Technologies and trends: an increasing number of material processing are based on lasers (soldering, cutting, 3D printing ...) and integrate Photonic sensors for quality and process control on the production and assembly lines.

Challenges: taking into account industrial constraints, in terms of productivity (3D printing) or data processing associated to automatic control and inspection.

Opportunities: SMEs, start-ups and high government funding form the innovation engine for the fourth industrial revolution in Germany.

Mobility and Transportation Systems

Technologies and trends: one on the current trends in the field of terrestrial transportation systems is the autonomous and intelligent vehicles. It's highly dependent on the "Photonics" technologies: sensors, cameras and LIDAR for observing the environment, LEDs and lasers for smart lighting and vehicle to car and infrastructure communications, displays for HCI, augmented/virtual reality, optical fibers for in-vehicle communications... "Fly by Light" is another trend in aeronautics: the optical fibers for in-vehicle communication infrastructure present several advantages in terms of weight and resistance to interference.

Smart and sustainable city

Market description: market with a medium volume composed by some niche markets and a good growth. Photonics have an important place in the building management but especially in the communication infrastructures, energy and light production.

Technologies, trends, challenges, opportunities: a significant trend is the development of the air quality management where Photonics provide solutions. The Li-Fi is an important response to the needs of interaction people or machine vs infrastructures. Photovoltaic is of course also a key technology.

Lightning and energy

Market description: Market with a large volume and strong growth. Photonics has strategic role in development and optimization of lightning sources. Dutch companies are quite active in these networks.

Technologies: spectroscopy, nanophotonics, fiberoptics, ...

Trends, challenges and Opportunities: The key interest is a solution for ecological and economical light production with user-defined parameters, as well as light distribution.

Creative industry

Market description: Market with medium volume but intensive growth, based on sectors where creativity and human talent is a primary commodity. This includes areas such as architecture, advertising, design, creation of computer games, film, television and music.

Technologies: lasers, displays, cameras and sensors, lightning, ...

Trends, challenges and Opportunities: described in relevant fields (lightning, displays, ...), 3D scanning and visualization in design, game and film industries.

Display technology

Market description: The display market covers the entire spectrum of display types and underlying technologies. It includes displays used in consumer products such as smartphone, TV, laptop, e-readers, as well as professional display solutions (digital theaters, laser shows, medical imaging etc.)

Technologies, trends, challenges, opportunities: The display technology witnessed a rapid transformation from conventional displays such as CRT to LCD, LED, OLED displays in the constant drive for high-resolution, energy-effective photo-realistic visual presentation of digital data.

Support for entrepreneurship in Photonics in Slovakia / Bratislava region

- Development of Slovak photonics cluster, a joint initiative of academic and industrial partners focused on the increase of awareness about Photonics, entrepreneurship and collaboration in this field. Contact & information: Dusan Chorvat – chorvat@ilc.sk
- Neulogy (<http://www.neulogy.com>) provides complex solutions and services rendered to institutions as well as to companies in the area of research, development and innovations; support of start-ups and entrepreneurship, science, R&D projects and infrastructure in a wide spectrum of science and technology areas (not Photonics-specific).
- SOVVA - Slovak Organization for Research and Development activities (<http://www.sovva.eu>) is a non-governmental organization of nationwide competence, established to promote R&D development in Slovakia by means of improving R&D capacities, bridging the academic and commercial areas while utilizing international experience and contacts.

SWEDEN

Photonics in Sweden

Photonics in Sweden has experienced a profound transformation since the years 2000. From a strong focus on telecom application driven by Ericsson and Telia Sonera, it has been diversifying to basically all main applications of photonics.

While keeping an impressive strength in the telecoms, Swedish photonics has a particularly large potential of growth in automation, green photonics and biophotonics.

Mature photonics technologies

Mature and edge photonics technologies in Sweden are e.g.: IR detection systems based on cameras from FLIR Systems and detectors from IR Nova IR sensors are also used in gas sensing devices from Sensair are also world leading in their field. In the telecom area there are many companies active from large suppliers and users like Ericsson and Telia to top notch component suppliers like Transmode (recently integrated in Infinera), Finisar and TE Connectivity. Proximion produces advanced fiber Bragg gratings and ACREO provides special optical fibers. Other components suppliers are in the laser field with diode-pumped solid-state lasers from Cobolt and the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH). Laser technology for medical diagnostics and treatment are developed at the Lund Laser Center and in spin-off companies like Spectracure. Surface-Plasmon Resonance detectors are provided from GE Healthcare Biosciences. Several research groups are working on thin-film photovoltaic as well as companies like Solibro and Midsummer. Many companies provide intelligent vision systems including SAAB Systems and eye tracking and eye control systems from Tobii. X-ray detector systems from several companies and high brilliance sources from Excillum.

PHOTONICS APPLICATIONS RELEVANT FOR THE FUTURE

Biophotonics

Sweden is the country of very important innovations in the life sciences, e.g. the pacemaker just to name one, and has a very strong academic research in medicine, veterinary, pharmaceuticals and agriculture. In that context, the about 40 and usually small Swedish companies active in biophotonics seem to have a large growth potential.

There is an increasing need for diagnostics and monitoring tools and the emergence of photonic innovations for the life science will be huge if an efficient dialogue is ensured between end-users, practitioners, technology providers and integrators. Obviously, the collaboration should also be, and is being, increased with other key technologies.

Automation

Automation of the industry is a key to maintain manufacturing or reindustrialize Western countries. It requires the use of advanced technology. For this machine vision and optical instruments to analyze and monitor industrial processes are increasingly used.

Swedish companies within automation have a turnover of about 5 billion Euros and our country has a long tradition of large companies and is very well positioned to lead "Photonics for factory automation".

Telecoms and Datacoms

The share of the telecoms in the Swedish photonics industry has decreased substantially since the early years 2000. Some very advanced companies and products have nevertheless been able to get good positions on the market, such as Transmode, Finisar Sweden, TE Connectivity and Proximion.

Ericsson has recently increased their interest in photonic technologies beyond fiber communication. It is likely that the building of 5G systems will require advanced integrated photonic integrated circuits and the involvement of Swedish companies.

Green Photonics

Sweden is one of the world's leading nations innovating, implementing and exporting Green Technologies, commonly known as Greentech or Cleantech. On the other hand, the use of photonics for Cleantech or green photonics is a field which is still in its infancy in Sweden.

Several Swedish companies develop new types of solar cells, e.g. CIGS thin-films or Graetzel type cells. There are excellent conditions in Sweden to make internet less energy hungry with photonic techniques. An interesting technology is the cleaning of water for developing countries and in the medical sector with light, either through UV LED or with sunlight as the company Solvatten is doing.

Security

Sweden is an important player in the development of security materials, both military and civil. In the defense sector, Saab is a big player stimulating surrounding companies. In the civilian sector, the company AHAB (now Hexagon) monitoring hydrographic topography should be mentioned.

Sweden has a particularly strong position in the field of thermal imaging with actors such as FLIR, IR Nova and Acreo.

Support for entrepreneurship in Photonics in Sweden

Essentially all universities have hubs and strategies to support entrepreneurship and start-up companies. These are not dedicated particularly to Photonics companies, Ideon in Lund and Lund "Nyföretagscentrum" as well as KTH Innovation, Stockholm Innovation and Growth (STING) have a very strong track record and they have helped tenth of photonics companies.

Spirit Ventures (Quan Funds LLC) is a venture capitalist who is specialized on financing companies which are active (or which are start-ups) in the KET (Key Enabling Technology) areas.

Contact & Information: PhotonicSweden, Isafjordsgatan 22, 164 40 Kista, Sweden
www.photonicsweden.com

UK

Introduction

UK Photonics is a significant and highly diversified industry directly employing ~70,000 people in 1500 manufacturing companies in all sectors from solid state lighting, next generation photovoltaics to lasers and imaging. Contributing £10.5bn to the UK economy, a similar level to the pharmaceutical industry, the Gross Value Aid for photonics is ~40% higher than the UK manufacturing average underpinning its essential contribution to the economy. Photonics Research from UK Universities also enjoys a global reputation for excellence with multiple world leading research institutes distributed throughout the country.

Mature photonics technologies

UK strengths and mature photonics industry sectors include:

- Lasers, particularly short pulse ultrafast, tuneable, industrial and fibre lasers
- Security and defence optoelectronics (e.g infrared imaging & range finding)
- Space optics (including imaging, communications and large scale optics)
- Compound semiconductors (e.g. Epitaxial growth, GaN on silicon LEDs, InP photonics integrated circuits)
- Gas sensing systems (remote and direct monitoring)
- Specialist Optical Coatings (high durability, infrared, multiband)
- Optical fibre (doped, high power and next generation geometries)

Significant advances are being made in extending the performance and capability of all photonics technologies in the UK to extend into new applications. One of the most significant overall trends is toward greater integration and design for integration at all levels to enable more complex photonics systems to be rapidly and economically fabricated.

PHOTONICS APPLICATIONS RELEVANT FOR THE FUTURE

Photonics for the Life Sciences

Optical imaging techniques provide easily-accessed in-depth imaging of the structures of the eye, surface tissues, mucosal, the gastrointestinal tract and vascular systems. These hold out the real promise of swifter and better diagnostic procedures with highly targeted treatment options enabled via photodynamic therapy.

Ultra-high bandwidth communications

Optical fibre and photonics technologies already provide the backbone of the modern communications network. The next great challenge is to extend current technology to provide another 1000 fold increase in bandwidth in the backbone network whilst providing lower cost and more energy efficient solutions in the datacentre and access networks.

Sensing technologies

The ability of photonics to sense at a distance, is critical to the development of next generation sensors that will enable self-driving cars, remote monitoring of emissions and enhanced security. Indeed sensors will be at the heart of the internet of things. Cost and energy efficiency will be key to the success of photonics sensing solutions which must compete against many alternative technologies.

Lighting

Lighting is not just a significant user of global energy it is has a significant influence on our sense of wellbeing as well as our safety. From car headlights to street lights to displays and interior and ambient lighting solid state LED lighting will be ubiquitous. Critical will be the adaptation of solid state lighting to utilize its full capability rather than just replace existing sources, with a second revolution coming form OLED and flexible lighting solutions

Security

Photonics is long been a key enabler in security and applications requiring rapid remote identification. The latest development includes the widespread deployment of laser systems to identify bottled liquids in airports and significant extension of smart image processing for early threat identification combining leading edge photonics and software development. The future will see further extension of technologies into the infrared.

Manufacturing

Laser and cameras are vital technologies for improving manufacturing productivity. Already deployed in key processes, lasers and imaging based feedback systems will penetrate much more widely in factories as utility in processing more materials, e.g. next generation composites and delivering return in more processes is demonstrated.

Support for entrepreneurship in Photonics in UK

The UK provide one of the most attractive business environments for company creation and growth in the world. The UK is ranked first in the EU for ease of doing business. Corporation tax will soon be just 20% ,with attractive incentives for investment such as Patent Box that further reduces tax on profits from products incorporating UK patented inventions as well as attractive R&D tax credits for off-setting the cost of product development.

Multiple grants are also available, particularly from Innovate_UK to support innovative product development. These include a range of collaborative grants and the popular SMART grant with multiple stages covering proof-of-market to proof-of-concept and development-of-prototype that can make a substantial difference to supporting a small company through the new product development process

Photonics4All is a European Horizon 2020 Outreach project, funded by the European Commission to promote photonics and light based technologies to young people, entrepreneurs and the general public across the EU. Photonics4all's unique selling point is that it will both develop a set of new promotional tools and apply them during a wide variety of outreach activities with different audiences.

*Discover our unique approach and check out our tools and events:
<http://photonics4all.eu/>*

Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light

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